

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

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Outreach and Dissemination Plan.

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About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan: i) **Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management**; ii) **Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production**; iii) **Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.**

Project consortium

Part . N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRA Transfert (IT) ****	France

* *Universities/veterinary schools*

** *Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences*

*** *Public and private advisory services Organisations*

**** *Knowledge transfer and Innovation organisations*

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ACTA	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AMs	Antimicrobials
AMU	Antimicrobial use
ANIS-EMA	AU Epidemiology and Management research unit
AU	Aarhus Universitet
AU-ANIS	AU Department of Animal Science
CA	Consortium Agreement
CIRAD	Centre de cooperation internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement
COGECA	General Committee for Agricultural Cooperation in the European Union
COPA	Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations
CU	Cardiff University
D	Deliverable
DGZ	Dierengezondheidzorg Vlaanderen VZW
DISTAL	Department of Agricultural and Food Science
DLS	Department of Livestock Sciences
DMP	Data Management Plan
EAAP	European Federation of Animal Science
EC	European Commission
EFFAB	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders
EIP-AGRI	The Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
EV-ILVO	Eigen vermogen van het instituut voor landbouw en visserijonderzoek
ExCom	Executive Committee
FABRE-TP	Farm Animal Breeding and Reproduction Technology Platform
FEUGA	Fundacion empresa Universidad Gallega
FIBL	Forschungsinstitut fur biologischen landbau stiftung
FSL	Food Safety Lab
FVE	Federation of Veterinarians of Europe
HUT	The James Hutton Institute
ICOH	International Conference on One Health
INRA	Institut national de la recherche agronomique
IPR	Intellectual property rights
IPUDC	Intellectual Property Use and Dissemination Committee
IT	INRA Transfert
ITAs	Technical Agricultural Institutes

MS	Milestone
NGOs	Non-governmental organizations
ODP	Outreach & Dissemination Plan
SAB	Stakeholder advisory board
SLU	Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet
UEVP	Union of European Veterinary Practitioners
ULIV	The University of Liverpool
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna
WBVR	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
WLR	Wageningen UR Livestock Research
WOHC	World One Health Congress
WP	Work Package
WR	Stichting Wageningen Research
WVAC	World Veterinary Association Congress
ZLTO	Zuidelijke land- en tuinbouworganisatie vereniging

1 Summary

Since ROADMAP has strong connections with the actors in the animal production system, it requires a detailed and targeted outreach and dissemination strategy to be developed at the onset of the project. Main targets and end-users of ROADMAP's tools, strategies and new knowledge are all the actors involved in the animal health sector and the food and drugs supply chains (farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmers' organisations, pharmaceutical companies, breeding, feeding industries, retailers and processors, policy makers) and the wider citizens concerned by the reduction of AMU. Therefore, an Outreach & Dissemination Plan (ODP) is designed to focus the dissemination strategy that are keys to acceptance. Optimized and quick utilisation of project outputs by all stakeholders requires an efficient strategy to disseminate ROADMAP information in relevant formats and through specific dissemination channels suitable for each stakeholder group.

2 Introduction

The ROADMAP Outreach and Dissemination Plan (ODP) is detailing the potential users, the communication and dissemination strategy, the potential use and the impacted area for each main result. The context of MS36 is built on the description given in the Description of Action (DoA) of the Grant Agreement. Therefore, ODP focuses on *communication and dissemination activities* both ensuring the aimed impacts will be achieved. The main objective of the outreach and dissemination strategy of ROADMAP is to ensure the uptake of integrative strategies developed within ROADMAP. This plan has a dynamic character which would follow the project progress, update as project evolves and guide ROADMAP partners so that the project impact could be maximised.

Figure 1 Dissemination and exploitation roadmap

2.1 Methods

The outreach and dissemination strategy will be carried out through 5 main tasks during the lifetime of the project.

- Stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange
- Online and offline, targeted communication activities
- Conventional and innovative dissemination activities
- Supportive training events

WP7 will be in close contact with all the WPs using a multi-actor approach by including stakeholders all throughout the project period. WP7 will promote the project, make project results available and facilitate their use, by providing a basis for stakeholder inclusion and knowledge exchange. Interactions with other relevant EU projects such as Star-Idaz, PROHEALTH, SAPHIR, Paragone, GenTORE, HealthyLivestock, One Health EJP, PanaMast, SIRCAH, DISARM, SONAR Global and liaisons with local and European networks will be implemented to promote the transfer of the results. Particular attention will be paid to liaising with the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance (JPI AMR).

3 ROADMAP Communication Tools and Activities

ROADMAP communication strategy targets stakeholders and end-users such as animal health professionals (veterinarians, technicians), farmers, breeding and feeding industries, pharmaceutical companies, retailers, processors, public authorities. Chosen communication tools and materials aim to target different audiences with different methods and channels selected to be used under ROADMAP project.

3.1 Project communication package

To make sure that the ROADMAP project appears coherent and consistent in all communication materials related to the project, a project identity and accompanying templates are produced. All participants are encouraged to follow the guidelines, for presentations, brochures, newsletters, publications etc. All official material for the European Commission and general public must be in accordance with the guidelines. The details of the project identity and communication package are given in detail in D7.2.

3.1.1 Project Logo

The ROADMAP logo has been designed for branding the project in all communication forms. Humans are in the center of the logo because they are the main elements of ROADMAP project which is about understanding behaviors and strategies of stakeholders) and also the main population threaten by the risks of antimicrobial resistance. The ROADMAP logo shows people on the crossroads that lead to different directions since we consider there is a diversity of pathways to foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials.

Animal heads are linked to circular paths referring to “ONE HEALTH” approach, highlighting the connection between human, health, animal health and the environment.

Figure 2 ROADMAP Logo with acronym only and including the title

Along with the ROADMAP logo, the EU flag should be visible on all communications from the ROADMAP project.

Link to graphic design of EU-projects:

http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information/logos/index_en.cfm

Please note that any **dissemination** and any **communication** activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must include this information:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817626.

3.1.2 Project Message

3.1.2.1 Tagline

The tagline describes the essence of the project in a short and understandable way, linking to why this is important for the target audiences. This is used on communication materials (website, brochure, presentations, etc.).

Currently used and proposed taglines:

“Rethinking of Antimicrobial Decision-systems in the Management of Animal Production”

“Understanding sociotechnical and socioeconomic drivers of AMU”

“Tailoring contextualized strategies to foster prudent AMU in diverse production systems in Europe and worldwide”

“Developing innovative socioeconomic and technical instruments to foster prudent AMU adapted to various production systems”

“Fighting against antimicrobial resistance by allowing cross-learning from diverse successful experiences”

“Encouraging a harmonization of AMU reduction trends across Europe”

“Favoring a global decrease of AMU in animal production”

3.1.2.2 Communication message

The communication message consists of one general message that should be further specified per target group. It will create the ‘external identity’ of the project. The message must be simple, clear and positive. This main communication message is:

ROADMAP aims to foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). ROADMAP will analyze sociotechnical and socioeconomic drivers of AMU and develop innovative strategies to promote prudent AMU, based on social sciences, interdisciplinary and participatory approaches.

3.2 Project website and online promotion activities

3.2.1 ROADMAP Public Website

The ROADMAP website is an important communication tool that requires continuous updating during the course of the project. It is the major communication and dissemination tool for the project. It presents the project objectives, work plan, highlights major results, presents the project partners and stakeholders, including electronic versions of training courses, links to other EU or international projects and stakeholder associations and contact details of relevant partners within the project. It also includes press releases, news and events, and a link to the YouTube channel where video materials, e-trainings and webinars are posted. The goal is to keep the website informative, up-to-date, inspiring and inclusive, so that it invites visitors to further engage with the project. Project website will be maintained for 2 more years after the project. Specifics of the website are given in D7.2 Website online and communication package.

The project website link is <https://www.roadmap-h2020.eu>. The site map for the website is shown below. In addition to provide basic information about the project, it will provide information about the involved countries, including the stakeholder activities. Further, it will provide up-to-date information about project progress and events, communication and dissemination materials.

Figure 3 Site map of ROADMAP

3.2.1.1 Stakeholders' Repository

The stakeholder's repository will be an online space within a specific section of the ROADMAP website where stakeholders can contribute, interact and stay tuned with the news, events and work developed through the project. It will be developed and managed by FEUGA, and it will include links to Facebook groups developed and managed by EFFAB to reach and foster interactions with stakeholders.

All the specifications and operational information is provided in deliverable D7.1 Stakeholders Engagement and MS35 Establishment of the stakeholder community. Opening of a private ROADMAP Stakeholder Page in preferred social media channel

3.2.1.2 ROADMAP Collaborative Platform developed by IT

All individual partners get access to the ROADMAP Collaborative Platform. This collaborative workspace is secured by password and only authorised partners can access this site. This platform is intended to enable collaboration between the different partners at all levels: Work Packages, Ex. Com, etc. and to trace document delivery. The access to the platform is organised with different permission levels. It should be used as

a central storage system of the project. Its functions include scientific, management administrative and financial information exchange and storage. INRA Transfert (IT) sets up the ROADMAP collaborative platform and will ensure its maintenance throughout the project. More details about the collaborative platform are given in deliverable D8.4.

Table 1: ROADMAP collaborative platform

Aim:	Partners can share and exchange information on the progress of the project in a secure way.
What:	Its functions include management, administrative and financial information and storage of interim EU Commission reports, minutes of the different meetings and deliverables.
How:	Accessible through the project's main website providing partners with one portal for all their ROADMAP internet (news updates, dissemination material, stakeholder exchange, etc.)
Who:	All project partners are responsible for providing input on their WPs
Time frame:	M6

3.2.2 Social media strategy and management

The project uses five different social media networks to target different stakeholder groups; YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and ResearchGate. Facebook is the most popular social network when targeting the end-users in many of the European countries. Twitter and LinkedIn are being used by companies, researchers and in particular by international, national and local policy and decision makers. It is also used by different umbrella organisations representing different parts of the society from producers to consumers. LinkedIn is targeting mainly professionals working in the sector and willing to read more about the technological and knowledge advances. It enables users to connect and share content with other professionals, including colleagues. ResearchGate is a media used mostly by researchers working in the public and private institutes including the R&I departments of companies. YouTube is used to share all kinds of audio-visual information for a broad range of stakeholders from the general public to scientists.

Table 2: ROADMAP Social Media accounts

SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNEL	ACCOUNT LINK
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Roadmap-H2020-2341808712742536/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/ROADMAP_H2020
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/roadmap-h2020
ResearchGate	https://www.researchgate.net/project/ROADMAP-Rethinking-Of-Antimicrobial-Decision-systems-in-the-Management-of-Animal-Production
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGRI_SjrqaheclVxCJHmPQ/about

All partners are encouraged to follow and share the above-mentioned accounts. In order to engage a wider audience through social media, their content must be relevant, valuable and usable for the different target groups. Different kinds of content could (among others) be:

- Publication of research results
- Writing articles or blogs
- Publication of whitepapers
- Publication of informative videos
- Photographs
- Promoting ROADMAP or other interesting events

The social media accounts can also be used to participate in discussions on relevant social platforms.

Table 3: Relevant keywords and tags

HASHTAGS	MENTIONS
#antimicrobialuse #AMU #AMR #animalproduction #foodsupplychain #innovative #antimicrobialresistance #AMUreduction #livestockproduction #livestockfarming #animalhealth #antimicrobials #livinglab #datacollection #costeffectiveness #dataanalysis #socsciAMR	@ROADMAP2019 @EFFAB @WUR @Inra_France @ACTA_asso @Cirad @LivUni @cardiffuni @JamesHuttonInst @UniboMagazine @AarhusUni @ILVOvlaanderen @fiblog @_SLU @ZLTO @FEUGA_20

In order to make full use of the communication channels, it is important to integrate the social media channels.

- Content on the ROADMAP website should be shareable for visitors, allowing them to share interesting information within their network.
- Social media feed should be placed on the homepage of the ROADMAP website.
- Social media buttons should be available in the ROADMAP newsletter.
- URLs or QR codes to the social media accounts or website could be used on offline communication, like brochures, posters or banners.
- ROADMAP activities, or related activities, have to be promoted via the social media accounts.

There are also some risks that could generate from social media shares. Therefore, it is important to see the possible risks and offer solutions beforehand. Table given below summarizes some of the main risks and solutions.

Table 4: Risks of social media usage in projects

RISK	SOLUTION
<u>Webcare is important</u> in order to manage your online reputation. If there is no control over what is being said about ROADMAP or related topics online, an unwanted message can spread very quickly.	<p>In all cases, it should be clear that thoughts are shared prior to replying to such messages. It could be very helpful to discuss it with the WP7 leader. This also depends on the severity of the unwanted message; in some cases, it could be better not to react.</p> <p>By monitoring what is going on online, it is possible to respond to potential crises within a short amount of time.</p> <p>When responding to unwanted messages it is not essential not to engage with people obvious bad intentions.</p> <p>Always show respect and be transparent.</p>
<u>Responding too quickly</u> to a tweet or post may compromise the quality of the response. However, waiting for days to get a tweet approved is not accepted either.	<p>As a starting point, a response should be sent within a couple of hours to a working day at the latest, depending on the subject.</p>

	The most important thing is to manage expectations and give relevant reactions to questions and comments.
Time, content and overview of online activities are key factors for success. If it is decided to use social media, it has to be taken care of on a regular basis. Social media accounts are not updated regularly, it will lose its impact and followers.	Choose wisely which channels will be used and how many. There are tools available to manage posting on social media accounts, for example Twitterfeed. To keep track of what is happening it is advisable to use tracking tools like Hootsuite, LinkedIn analytics, Facebook analytics, Google analytics or YouTube analytics.
Manage the opinions and expectations from stakeholders. The project is designed in order to achieve a maximum interaction with stakeholders, but many different views/opinions could also be difficult to manage; how do you coop with opposite opinions? And what do you do when stakeholders feel like nothing was done with their ideas/opinions?	In order to manage the stakeholders should be included from the beginning, in order that they feel like they have had an influence on the direction of the project. Depending on the number and kind of stakeholders, WP7 should prepare a plan to manage expectations. An option could be to organize evaluations with the stakeholders.

3.2.3 Online promotion materials

3.2.3.1 Newsletters

To spread project news to partners, stakeholders and other groups of interest, 6 digital newsletters are planned to be prepared. Items for the newsletter will be assembled by EFFAB, who will also facilitate the distribution. All partners are strongly encouraged to share articles and other news items to be published in the newsletter. The newsletter will be created and distributed by using the online tool MailChimp. Updates of the newsletter will be mentioned on the website and other social media to increase awareness. People can subscribe for the newsletter via the ROADMAP homepage. Furthermore, partners and stakeholders are encouraged to share the newsletter within their network.

Table 5: Provisional Newsletter publication dates

ISSUE NO	PROJECT MONTH	PUBLICATION DATE
ROADMAP News 1	M12	May 2020
ROADMAP News 2	M24	May 2021
ROADMAP News 3	M30	November 2021
ROADMAP News 4	M36	May 2022
ROADMAP News 5	M42	November 2022
ROADMAP News 6	M48	May 2023

3.2.3.2 Audio-visual documents

Audio-visual media in form of interviews, presentations with commentaries and session recordings will be prepared during the course of the project for creating awareness, communication, dissemination and training purposes. In addition, a ROADMAP animated video will be prepared to raise awareness to AMR and communicate the integrative strategies to public and policy makers. ROADMAP animation video will be communicated through ROADMAP TV at YouTube channel and will be promoted through social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) of the project as well as EFFAB and FABRE-TP networks.

3.2.3.3 Press releases

Press releases on the project's actions will be created, publishing interesting results and progress. All press releases will be published on an international level, targeting the broader press by using the website, social media accounts and the network of ROADMAP partners and stakeholders. Partners will assure translation into national language.

Press releases, news and events about the project will be shared with the online magazines that have high number of audiences in the field of animal health and AMR. Popular agricultural media channels and online magazines will be used to reach to a wider audience.

Table 6: ROADMAP press releases

Aim:	Inform wider society about ROADMAP project's aim and results through magazines such as Feedstuffs, Agrifutures, Farmers Weekly
What:	Information about AMR
How:	Through press releases, articles and news
Who:	EFFAB and all partners
Time frame:	M1-M48

3.2.4 Offline tools and activities

3.2.4.1 Project Brochure

A brochure will be prepared in English to promote the ROADMAP project to potential stakeholders at M8. The brochure aims to create awareness to the project objectives and impact targeting different stakeholders. It will be distributed during conferences, workshops and other awareness events. It will also be sent to the project partners and is aimed to be translated to various European languages.

A second brochure will be prepared at the last year of the project. This will be used for the dissemination of the project outcomes and results. It is aimed to be available in English and other European languages.

3.2.4.2 Banners

During the course of the project 2 banners will be prepared to be used during conferences, workshops, profile raising events and stakeholder activities. First banner will give information on the aim and objectives of the project whereas the second one will give brief information on the outcomes of the project.

3.2.4.3 Infographic

An infographic will be prepared with the aim to simplify and visualize the results of the project at the last year of the project. It will target the policymakers and the general public as well as end-users.

3.2.4.4 Profile Raising Event

At the beginning of the project a profile-raising activity will be held to communicate about the project to relevant stakeholders next to an international event like annual meetings of Federation of Veterinarians of Europe (FVE) or Union of European Veterinary Practitioners (UEVP), COPA-COGECA, International Conference on One Health (ICOH).

Table 7: Possible international events for profile raising events of ROADMAP

WHEN	EVENT	WHERE
06-08 April 2020	World Veterinary Association Congress (WVAC)	Auckland, New Zealand
21-22 May 2020	International Conference on One Health ICOH	London, UK
27-28 May 2020	EFFAB-FABRE TP AGM	Evora, Portugal
14-18 June 2020	6th World One Health Congress (WHOC20)	Edinburgh, Scotland
31 August – 04 September 2020	EAAP 2020	Porto, Portugal

4 ROADMAP Dissemination strategy

The main targeted end-users of ROADMAPS tools, strategies and new knowledge are all the actors involved in the animal health sector and the food and drugs supply chains (farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmers' organisations, pharmaceutical companies, breeding, feeding industries, retailers and processors, policy makers) and the wider citizens concerned by the AMR issue. Chosen dissemination methods aim to target different audiences with different events, materials and tools with ROADMAP outcomes and results. The dissemination strategy is mainly based on the results of the ROADMAP research and the relevant deliverables to be developed during the course of the project. It is devoted to ensuring the uptake of integrated strategies developed within ROADMAP and their wide-ranging coverage.

4.1 Dissemination goals

ROADMAP results and outputs will have an impact on different levels of actors in the society ranging from global impacts to highly specialized ones. In Figure 4, different levels of target groups are given in relation to the dissemination goals of ROADMAP based on its expected results. ROADMAP aims to provide tools and results starting from the farmer itself, as the main end-user of ROADMAP strategies, to the general public and human/animal populations in the world.

Figure 4 ROADMAP dissemination goals targeted to different levels of stakeholders

4.2 Targeted dissemination tools

ROADMAP will make use of different interactive and innovative dissemination methods and tools in order to target different stakeholders and actors. These tools will ensure that key stakeholders are aware of ROADMAP results and know-how to be actively involved in project activities and training. The following table lists the target audiences and the specific tools to reach out to them:

Figure 5 ROADMAP targeted dissemination strategy

4.2.1 Peer-reviewed and Scientific papers

ROADMAP results will be disseminated in accordance with the ODP to targeted stakeholders by publications in high-ranked peer reviewed journals and attendance to international scientific conferences. Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals will contribute to the Green or Gold model of open access journals and they will be communicated in congresses (oral communications and posters).

For peer-reviewed scientific publications, all partners will apply the Horizon 2020 Open Access Policy and deposit scientific peer reviewed publications (machine-readable electronic copy of the published version) in an institutional repository of their research institution. Where this is not available to partners, an alternative repository will be identified so that all scientific publications are included in the European research e- infrastructure of OpenAIRE. ROADMAP will encourage gold open access publishing. Owing to the four-year duration of ROADMAP, at least 6 peer reviewed outputs are expected during the project, with several more published after the project concludes. Funding for Gold Open Access will be sought from other sources after the project concludes (e.g. partner's institutional budgets), and Green Open Access (self-archiving) undertaken if funding is not found.

4.2.2 Practice abstracts and Operational Groups

Disseminating about project activities and results is much easier through the use of a common format. The EIP-AGRI common format facilitates knowledge flows on innovative and practice-oriented projects from the start until the end of the project. The use of this format also enables farmers, advisers, researchers and all other actors across the EU to contact each other. Operational Groups are regional or national practice-oriented innovation projects supported by rural development programmes under the Common Agricultural

Policy. The EIP-AGRI helps these projects to work in synergy with other interactive innovation projects under Horizon 2020.

At least ten “practice abstracts” will be delivered in the common EIP format to feed into the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) ‘Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability’ for broad dissemination. Common EIP format is given in Annex 1. The prepared practice abstracts are aimed to be translated in different European languages whereas appropriate.

In addition to EIP Common format, a ROADMAP common template will be prepared for practice abstracts to be published at the end of the project in the form of a booklet.

4.2.3 Policy briefs

A policy brief is a concise summary of a particular issue, the policy options to deal with it, and some recommendations on the best option. It is aimed at government policymakers and others who are interested in formulating or influencing policy.¹ ROADMAP policy briefs will be prepared in the second half of the project. A specific ROADMAP policy template will be prepared to have a common format and the policy briefs will be published in the form of a booklet to be distributed in the networking events.

4.2.4 Workshops, Living Labs and Networking activities

Various workshops with different purposes will be organised during the project lifetime. There will be involvement of different WPs and partners in the organisation of these workshops. Workshops will be organised to increase the interaction with the stakeholders, to increase the dissemination of project results to the scientific community and end-users.

In each country where research is going to be undertaken, strong collaborations between scientists and stakeholders and animal health professionals are going to be implemented, through the conceptual and methodological framework of “living labs”. The Living labs will allow a mutual learning process across different production systems and sectors. International joint reflective workshops will be organised for the partners from the different Living labs.

Networking drinks and lunch meet-up will be organised with selected highly influential stakeholder representatives like umbrella organisations and big pharmaceutical companies, policymakers and media representatives twice during the course of the project.

ROADMAP final conference is intended to be organised next to an international scientific conference like WVAC where the outcomes of the project could be shared with the scientific world and top industry representatives. A final conference at the end of the project will be organised to present the outcomes of the project to stakeholders with a specific policy side-event.

4.2.5 ROADMAP Trainings

Training workshops will be organised to target animal health professionals and end-users in order to facilitate the uptake of the integrated strategies by using the material generated within the project. Within the project course, a set of four training sessions will be carried out in the locations of the case studies proposed in the project.

The adaptation of the materials developed will compose training modules. These modules will be focused on the results generated during the project related to the Solutions (Pillar 2, WPs 3 and 4) and Evaluation and recommendations (Pillar 3, WP 5 and 6). In this context, the development of guidelines on how to conduct Living labs and the data collection during implementation under WP4 will be done in exchange with

¹ <http://www.fao.org/3/i2195e/i2195e03.pdf>

WP3 and WP7. These Living labs will take place in the national case studies in order to develop new comprehensive approaches to foster prudent AMU. In the living labs, stakeholders such as farmers and vets will be included. Co-learning events for farmers, vets and advisory services (3 exchanges are foreseen) organised by WP4 as cross country events, targeting farmers from Switzerland, France, Denmark and Italy will be facilitated by WP7. These co-learning events aim to explore, what strategies farmers and vets implemented to foster prudent AMU. A mini webinar series will complement the training to the industrial stakeholders (breeding, feeding, pharmaceuticals, farm technologies, etc). The webcasts and other training materials will be published at the ROADMAP TV.

4.3 Management of the research data and dissemination of own results

ROADMAP will follow principles of good data management that incorporate management of data at every stage of the data lifecycle, covering data capture; storage; preservation; access; reuse; and where appropriate, disposal. The project will draw up a first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) as deliverable (D8.3) at month 6 of the project to ensure compliance with guidance from the Pilot on Open Research Data and H2020 Open Access policy. This version will be updated when necessary in the course of the project, in particular once the extent of the dataset from each WP becomes clear, and if there are any changes in consortium policies or external factors requiring an update. Updated versions would be provided at every periodic reporting.

Project outputs such as presentations, brochures, and publications, as well as videos, Practical abstracts, Research and innovation protocols, etc will be made available on the ROADMAP official website. Dissemination of knowledge stemming from ROADMAP (outputs) is aimed at maximising the open access to ROADMAP's results. Fundamental scientific results will be freely disseminated through appropriate channels: scientific publications, presentations at international conferences and workshops, etc. Regarding Living Labs, intellectual property rights about the service innovation will be discussed for each Living Lab. ROADMAP will ensure that generic knowledge and tutorials will be diffused on an open basis from each Living Lab.

ROADMAP dissemination of own results is outlined in detail within the Consortium Agreement (CA) section 9.4.2.1 paragraph 2.

“Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given, including copy of the proposed publication, to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the intended date of publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.”

4.4 Strategy for knowledge management and protection

ROADMAP knowledge will be managed by the partners contributing to generate it with the support of the Executive Committee (ExCom) and the Intellectual Property Use and Dissemination Committee (IPUDC) – to be appointed. Knowledge management will comply with the rules established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). The IPUDC members are representatives of the partners' technological transfer departments. When necessary and upon request of the ExCom, the IPUDC will screen the deliverables, planned publications and progress reports to identify the possible IP and the potential exploitation of the results. Then, it will advise the ExCom and concerned parties. The concerned parties will review the results and will choose either to disseminate (i.e. prepare a publication) or to seek appropriate protection actions of the results and eventually a plan for their best exploitation.

Figure 6 Strategy for ROADMAP knowledge management and protection

ROADMAP will follow the H2020 guidelines on Open Access to scientific publication and research data... All the resulting peer reviewed scientific articles will be published at least in “green” open access. For ROADMAP, in case of results in rapidly evolving domains, Gold Open Access will be used. If relevant, patent applications will be filed in if the invention meets patentability criteria and if it displays enough commercial potential. Otherwise, all foreground generated by the project will be freely accessible.

4.5 Evaluation

As mentioned, the success of ROADMAP project is highly related to the extent of stakeholder involvement. A maximal stakeholder inclusion is required in order to create the most beneficial effect on the quality and applicability of the tools and other outcomes, and to get a wider view on different ideas and perspectives. Also, it will guarantee the relevance of the tools and create conditions for rapid uptake and deployment of them in the industry. The outreach, dissemination and training activities mentioned in this plan should help to achieve this. To be able to know whether the communication has been used effectively, it is important to evaluate the use of communication means.

Table 8: Evaluation tools for the communication and dissemination activities

ACTIVITY	EVALUATION TOOL
Social Media	The number of interactions (views, mentions, re-tweets, etc)
ROADMAP Website	Google Analytics will be used to evaluate the number of new visits, average time per visit, number of visits to multiple pages, etc.
Newsletter	MailChimp offers an analytical tool to keep track on the number of people opening the newsletter, direct feedback, number of downloads
Brochures, flyers and other marketing materials	Number of downloads and visualizations, direct feedback
Stakeholder E-Platform	Number of participants, visits, feedbacks and information exchanges
Conferences and events	Number of participants to the meeting, Survey after the conference or event
Peer-reviewed / Scientific papers	Number of citations
Workshops and training sessions	Number of participants, Surveys after the workshop or training are spread among the participants in order to receive feedback

4.6 Annual Outreach, Dissemination and Training plans

This chapter summarizes the activities planned for each year of the ROADMAP project. Upon completion of the first year, it will be updated with the subsequent year and so on in order to properly monitor and evaluate the progress.

4.6.1 Year 1 (01/06/2019-31/05/2020)

Table 9: Deliverables and milestones of WP7 for the first project year

DELIVERABLES/MILESTONES	RESULTS
D7.1 ROADMAP guidelines for recruitment of stakeholders	These guidelines will include: i) Composition and roles of the stakeholders community, ii) Detailed rules of governance of the SAB (decision making processes, dependencies with the other WPs, etc.), iii) Operational management procedures at regional and European levels, and iv) creation of templates making possible the work harmonisation.
D7.2 Website online and communication package	ROADMAP website will be launched, and communication documents will be issued
D7.3 Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results-ODP	Document detailing ROADMAP main results, their potential users and their strategy of dissemination
MS35 Establishment of the stakeholder community	Opening of a private ROADMAP Stakeholder Page in preferred social media channel
MS36 Outreach and Dissemination Plan	ODP will be prepared and published

Figure 7 Timeline of outreach and dissemination activities and tools for year 1

4.7 Results & Implications

The main result and implication of the outreach and dissemination strategy is to ensure and maximise the uptake of the ROADMAP results by the end-users. In order to contribute to achieving the expected impacts

of the project the results will be used in various forms of dissemination materials and tools targeting different audiences as given in Figure 4. The summary of results and implications per expected impact is given in the table below.

Table 10 Summary of results and implications of ROADMAP Dissemination strategy

Expected Impact	Target audience	Outputs by WP7	Dissemination Media
Contribute to the fight against AMR arising from farmed animal production	All stakeholders	All dissemination materials	All dissemination channels
Develop options for reducing the use of AMs in farming	Animal health professionals, farm managers/advisors, farmers, breeding and feeding companies, pharmaceuticals	Practice abstracts; workshops and trainings, audio-visuals and brochures	Website, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, EIP-AGRI, international and national events
Provide roadmaps and scenarios for transition towards prudent use, enhance capacities of farmers for innovation and AMU change	Farmers	Practice abstracts; workshops and trainings, audio-visuals and brochures	Website, Facebook, EIP-AGRI, national and regional events, stakeholders' community on facebook
Provide new tools for preventive approach of animal health, and new professional and business models for veterinary practices	Veterinarians	Guidelines, practice abstracts, workshops, trainings, specialized brochures	Website, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, EIP-AGRI, emails, national and international events, stakeholders' community on facebook
Propose new contractual instruments and incentives to engage animal health professionals and stakeholders in a shared process of reducing AMU	Upstream and downstream industries (pharmaceuticals, breeding, feeding companies, food chain)	Guidelines, strategies, specialized fact sheets, workshops, webinars	Website, Twitter, LinkedIn, ResearchGate, EIP-AGRI, emails, national and international events, stakeholders' community on facebook
Propose policy measures for harmonizing AMU practices across Europe, and homogenize AMU reduction trends	Policy makers, decision makers, influencers, professional bodies	Policy briefs, press releases, guidelines, infographics, networking activities, audio-visuals	Website, Twitter, popular press, YouTube channel
Promote AMR and AMU research networks at national & international levels	Academia/Researchers	Peer-reviewed articles, posters, oral presentations at scientific events, e-book of abstracts	Website, ResearchGate, emails, international conferences
Raising awareness of animal health professionals and stakeholders, and large end-user community	All actors	All communication tools	All communication channels

5 Partners involved in the work

All partners of ROADMAP are involved in the communication and dissemination activities. However, there are some of the partners who carry out these activities. Below is the list of main partners involved in ROADMAP Outreach and Training.

EFFAB, as the WP Leader, is responsible for the whole WP7 Outreach, dissemination and training and related tasks to be carried out. **FEUGA** is the deputy leader of WP7.

FEUGA is responsible for the Stakeholders community creation and management. **EFFAB, ACTA, CIRAD, HUT, UNIBO, EV-ILVO, SLU, ZLTO, DGZ** will be also involved in this task.

EFFAB and **INRA and FEUGA** will be involved in communication activities.

EFFAB and **FEUGA, INRA, ACTA, CIRAD, ULIV, CU, HUT, UNIBO, AU, EV-ILVO, FIBL, WR, SLU, ZLTO, DGZ, IT** are responsible of the dissemination of project results.

FEUGA and **INRA, ACTA, CIRAD, ULIV, CU, HUT, UNIBO, AU, EV-ILVO, FIBL, WR, ZLTO, EFFAB, DGZ, IT** are responsible for the Innovation, IPR management and exploitation of ROADMAP outcomes.

6 Conclusion

WP7 will publicise the project, make project results available and facilitate their use, by providing a basis for stakeholder inclusion and knowledge exchange. WP7 will use conventional and innovative communication and dissemination tools including digital media channels, audio-visual materials, webinars, workshops, publications, practice abstracts and trainings to efficiently reach out to each target audience group. All the organisation and creation of these activities and tools will be managed under the Outreach and Dissemination Plan.

The Outreach and Dissemination plan explains the activities dedicated to the different target audiences and thereby reflects how a high transparency is reached during the project lifetime. It shows the European Commission and the stakeholders how the project will **report**, how will it **handle results**, how will the stakeholders be **informed**, where the project will be **presented** and how the project will **measure** and **improve** the communication and dissemination tools, and how the project will **ensure the sharing (communication and dissemination) of the research results with the identified potential users**.

7 Appendix

Annex 1 Common EIP-AGRI format for “Practice abstracts”

Practice "abstract" 1:	<i>Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.</i>		
Short title in <u>English</u>		Recommended	0 character(s) / 150
Short summary for practitioners in <u>english</u> on the <u>(final or expected) outcomes</u> (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). <i>Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English</i> This summary should at least contain the following information: – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using <u>a direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.	Recommended	0 character(s) / 1500	
Short title in <u>native language</u>		Mandatory	0 character(s) / 150
Short summary for practitioners in <u>native language</u> (<i>can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English</i>) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). This summary should at least contain the following information: – Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final) – The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results? This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using <u>a direct and easy understandable language</u> and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.	Mandatory	0 character(s) / 1500	

